

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTICS OF 5-ARYLAZO-2,4-DIHYDROXY-6-METHYLPYRIMIDINES (II)

Sl. No.	X, Y	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis%	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	H	302-4	73	N, 24.35	24.67
2.	2-CH ₃	207-9	50	N, 22.95	22.85
3.	3-CH ₃	179 ^d	54	N, 22.95	22.91
4.	4-CH ₃	185 ^d	50	N, 22.95	23.07
5.	2-Cl	203-4	75	Cl, 13.42	13.49
6.	3-Cl	172	77	Cl, 13.42	13.28
7.	4-Cl	235 ^d	73	Cl, 13.42	13.44
8.	2-Br	205	78	Br, 25.89	26.10
9.	4-Br	220 ^t	75	Br, 25.89	24.92
10.	2-NO ₂	217-19	76	N, 25.45	25.40
11.	3-NO ₂	253	71	N, 25.45	25.53
12.	4-NO ₂	310	70	N, 25.25	25.58
13.	2,5-(Cl) ₂	303 ^d	63	Cl, 23.74	22.48
14.	2,5-(Br) ₂	300 ^d	65	Br, 41.24	41.09

^d—melts with decomposition.

TABLE 3—CHARACTERISTICS OF 5-ARYLAZO-4,6-DIMETHYL-2-HYDROXYPYRIMIDINES (III)

Sl. No.	X, Y	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis%	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	H	239	70	N, 24.57	24.63
2.	2-CH ₃	257 ^d	51	N, 23.14	23.28
3.	4-CH ₃	242	55	N, 23.14	22.98
4.	2-OCH ₃	255 ^d	48	N, 21.71	21.56
5.	4-OCH ₃	288	57	N, 21.71	21.77
6.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	318 ^d	55	N, 20.58	20.79
7.	2-Cl	230	65	Cl, 13.36	13.15
8.	3-Cl	210	72	Cl, 13.36	13.15
9.	4-Br	237	63	Br, 26.05	26.17
10.	2-NO ₂	298	70	N, 26.52	26.68
11.	3-NO ₂	304	78	N, 26.52	26.37
12.	4-NO ₂	303 ^d	69	N, 26.52	26.60
13.	2,5-(Br) ₂	308 ^d	77	Br, 41.45	41.80
14.	2,5-(Cl) ₂	284 ^d	79	Cl, 23.84	23.85

^d—melts with decomposition.

Method for reduction: A solution of I (X=Y=H) (2.29 g; 0.01 g mole) in acetic acid (20 ml) was added to a suspension of pure zinc (1.31 g; 0.02 g atom) in water (10-15 ml) slowly and with constant stirring. The mixture was first stirred at room temperature for 30-40 min and then heated on boiling water bath for 2-3 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered and the residue washed twice with water. Combined filtrate was neutralized with dilute NaHCO₃ and solid separated was crystallized from ethanol to give crystals, m.p. 285° (d), (yield 51%) which was identified as 2,5-diamino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine [lit. m.p.⁶ 281-2° (d)]. (Found: N, 40.3. Calcd. for C₅H₈N₄O; N, 40.01%).

Similarly II (X=Y=H) and III (X=Y=H) were reduced and characterised by m.p. and elemental analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee for facilities. One of the authors (V. K.) is thankful to

University Grants Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. V. K. MAHESH, R. N. GOYAL, and (Mrs.) RAMA GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 738.
2. L. E. BRADY and R. M. HERBST, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 922.
3. *Organic Syntheses*, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, Collective Vol. II, p. 422.
4. G. M. KOSOLAPOFF and C. H. ROY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 1895.
5. KENZU SHIRAKAWA, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1953, **73**, 635.

Search for New Hypoglycemic Agents.

Part—VII: Coumarinylsulphonyl Ureas,

Semicarbazides and Semicarbazones

M. IMTIAZ HUSAIN* and (Miss) KIRAN BALA GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University,
Lucknow-226 007

and

R. C. SRIVASTAVA

Division of Experimental Medicine, C. D. R. I., Lucknow

Manuscript received 9 March 1981, revised 18 March 1982,
accepted 12 August 1982

SULPHONYLUREAS^{1,2,3} have long been known in the therapy of diabetes. It has recently been reported that sulphonamido coumarins⁴ possess antidiabetic activity comparable to that of chlorpropamide. Moreover, some sulphonyl semicarbazides⁵ and semicarbazones have also exhibited marked hypoglycemic activity. Hence, the title compounds were prepared with a view to study their hypoglycemic efficacy.

4,5,7-Trimethylcoumarin on chlorosulphonation gave 4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl chloride, which on treatment with ammonia was converted to the corresponding sulphonamide. The latter was allowed to react with ethyl chloroformate in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ and dry acetone to yield ethyl N-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) carbamate. The carbamate on condensation with various amines and hydrazines gave coumarinylsulphonyl ureas and coumarinylsulphonyl semicarbazides, respectively. Also, the treatment of the carbamate with hydrazine hydrate afforded a semicarbazide which was condensed with different aldehydes or ketones to furnish coumarinylsulphonyl semicarbazones.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The structures of compounds were confirmed by ir spectra and elemental analysis.

4,5,7-Trimethylcoumarin : It was prepared by the modification of the method reported earlier⁶. Polyphosphoric acid (174.5 g) was added to a solution of 3,5-dimethylphenol (12.0 g; 0.1 mole) in ethylacetate (12.7 ml). The resulting mixture was heated at 75-80° with stirring for 20 min and thereafter poured into ice cold water. A pale yellow solid, thus obtained crystallised from dilute ethanol, yield 40%, m.p. 175-176° (lit.⁷ m.p. 176°).

4,5,7-Trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl chloride : 4,5,7-Trimethylcoumarin (18.8 g; 0.1 mol) was kept in a freezing mixture (-8°) and chlorosulphonic acid (23.3 ml; 0.2 mol) was added to it dropwise. The resulting mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temp. It was subsequently heated on a water bath at 80° for a few min and then poured into crushed ice. The product crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 177-178°, yield 60%. (Found : C, 50.00; H, 3.44. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₁O₄SO₂Cl; C, 50.26; H, 3.84%).

4,5,7-Trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonamide : 4,5,7-Trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl chloride (0.01 mol) was treated with an excess of aq. ammonia. The resulting mixture was heated on a water bath for a few min. The product obtained on addition of water to the mixture crystallised from water, m.p. 185°, yield 80%. (Found : N, 4.95. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₃O₄NS; N, 5.24%). NMR (CDCl₃) : δ (ppm) 1.25-1.32 (6H, d, 2 CH₃), 1.20 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.2 (1H, s, H₈), 7.4 (1H, s, H₆) and 4.5-4.6 (2H, broad hump, NH₂).

Ethyl N-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) carbamate : A mixture of 4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonamide (21.2 g), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (27.6 g) and dry acetone (25 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr. Thereafter, ethyl chloroformate (23.6) was added to the refluxing mixture over 1-5 hr. It was further refluxed for 3 hr and then evaporated to dryness. The residue obtained was dissolved in 50 ml of water and 1 N HCl was added to the solution till pH 8-8.5 was attained. After standing overnight, the solution was filtered and the filtrate acidified with 5 N HCl to attain pH 4, when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 178°. (Found : N, 3.65. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₇O₆NS; N, 4.13%).

N¹-(4,5,7-Trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl)-N³-aryl/alkyl ureas : Ethyl N-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) carbamate (0.003 mole) and an appropriate amine (0.003 mole) were refluxed in anhydrous toluene or benzene (10 ml) for 4 hr on a water bath. A solid was obtained on cooling which crystallised from ethanol or methanol.

Melting points and pertinent data of the compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

N¹-(Phenyl/p-tolyl)-N³-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) semicarbazides : These were prepared analogously from ethyl N-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) carbamate and phenyl/p-tolyl hydrazine. The two semicarbazides thus obtained are :

TABLE 1—N¹-[(4,5,7-TRIMETHYL-8-COUMARINYL-SULPHONYL)]-N³-ALKYL/ARYL UREAS

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	% N Found (Calcd.)	Reduction in Blood sugar in rats %
1.*	p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	182	88	6.55 (7.00)	15
2.*	C ₆ H ₅	205	90	6.88 (7.25)	8
3.*	C ₃ H ₇	181-183	80	7.9± (8.28)	8
4.*	n-C ₄ H ₉	174	90	7.99 (8.33)	10
5.	o-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	178	70	6.75 (7.00)	10
6.	p-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	180	60	6.33 (6.73)	0
7.	o-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	185	65	6.30 (6.73)	—
8.	p-ClC ₆ H ₄	194	80	6.25 (6.66)	—
9.	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	180	85	5.47 (6.17)	—
10.	C ₆ H ₁₁	188	70	6.50 (7.14)	10
11.	p-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	179-181	60	9.41 (9.72)	—
12.	2,4-(O ₂ N) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	189	40	9.34 (9.70)	—
13.	2,3-Br ₂ C ₆ H ₃	188	50	5.14 (5.55)	—
14.*	p-BrC ₆ H ₄	190	50	5.71 (6.00)	—

* Showed ir spectral bands at 1190 cm⁻¹ (sec SO₂NH-), 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and 3250 cm⁻¹ (-NH).

I. N¹-(Phenyl)-N³-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) semicarbazide, m.p. 200°, yield 50%. (Found : N, 10.00. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₉O₅N₃S; N, 10.4%). IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) : 1700 (C=O), 1200 (sec SO₂NH-) and 3200-3340 (-NH-NH-).

It caused reduction in blood sugar in rats by 5%.

II. N¹-(p-Tolyl)-N³-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) semicarbazide, m.p. 191°, yield 55%. (Found : N, 9.84. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₁O₅N₃S; N, 10.12%). IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) : 1700 (C=O), 1160-1180 (sec SO₂NH-) and 3100-3400 (-NH-NH-).

It reduced the blood sugar in rats by 11%.

N³-(4,5,7-Trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) semicarbazide : A mixture of ethyl N-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) carbamate (0.03 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (100%; 0.03 mole) was refluxed in absolute ethanol (25 ml) for 8 hr. The product crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 165°, yield 60%. (Found : N, 12.52. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₈O₅N₃S; N, 12.9%).

NOTES

TABLE 3—GROSS CNS OBSERVATIONS AND ALD₅₀ OF SOME COMPOUNDS

Compd. No.	Gross CNS observations										ALD ₅₀ mg/kg i.p.
	Dose 464 mg/kg i.p.					Dose 1000 mg/kg i.p.					
	S.M.A.	Reactivity	Death	Writhing	Other effects	S.M.A.	Reactivity	Death	Writhing	Other effects	
1.	↓	↓	0/4	(+)	(-)	↓	↓	0/4	(+)	Respiration	1000
2.	↓	↓	0/4	(+)	Respiration	↓	↓	2/4	(+)	(-)	1000
3.	↓	↓	0/4	(+)	"	↓	↓	0/4	(-)	Respiration	1000
4.	↓	↓	0/4	(-)	(-)	↓	↓	0/4	(-)	(-)	650
14.	↓	↓	0/4	(-)	(-)	↓	↓	0/4	(-)	(-)	1000
17.	↓	↓	2/4	(+)	Respiration	↓	↓	0/4	(+)	(-)	870
18.	↑	↑	0/4	(+)	(-)	↑	↑	0/4	(+)	(-)	1000
19.	↑	↑	0/4	(+)	Respiration	↑	↑	0/4	(+)	Respiration	1000
21.	↑	↑	0/4	(-)	Respiration	↑	↑	0/4	(-)	"	1000
22.	↑	↑	0/4	(-)	(-)	↑	↑	0/4	(-)	(-)	1000

↓ = decreased; ↑ = increased; (+) = present; (-) = not affected.
* Correspond to Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 2—N⁴-(4,5,7-TRIMETHYL-8-COUMARINYLSULPHONYL) SEMICARBAZONES

Sl. No.†	R ¹	R ²	m. p. °C	Yield %	%N Found (Calcd.)
15.*	C ₆ H ₅	H	180	65	9.64 (10.17)
16.*	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	180	50	9.00 (9.99)
17.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	H	145	50	9.41 (9.83)
18.	<i>p</i> -NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	182	75	12.36 (12.67)
19.	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	176	40	9.32 (9.74)
20.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	120	95	9.45 (9.83)
21.*	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	152	50	8.14 (8.58)
22.	C ₃ H ₁₀		175	50	10.01 (10.37)

* Showed IR spectral bands at 1200 cm⁻¹ (ν SO₂NH-), 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 3100-3400 cm⁻¹ (ν NH) and 1600-1660 cm⁻¹ (ν N=C-).

† Correspond to those in Table-1.

N⁴-(4,5,7-Trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) semicarbazones: Equimolar amounts of N⁴-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) semicarbazide and an aldehyde/ketone were refluxed in absolute ethanol in the presence of a drop of glacial acetic acid for 4 hr. The product crystallised from ethanol.

Analysis, melting points and yield of the prepared semicarbazones are presented in Table 2.

Bioassay :

(a) **Hypoglycemic activity :** The two compounds (I and II above) and eight compounds (Table 1)

were tested for hypoglycemic activity. They showed very little activity.

(b) **CNS activity :** For studying their action on the central nervous system (CNS), the compounds were administered to albino mice in different doses and their behavioural changes in spontaneous motor activity and reactivity to sound and touch were noted. Ten compounds (Table 3) were screened for CNS activity. They showed very little CNS depressant or stimulant activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. V. S. Misra, Head, Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow for necessary facilities and to the Vice-Chancellor, Lucknow University for the award of a U. G. C., Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (K. B. G.).

References

- J. MARCO and I. VALVERDE, *Diabetologia*, 1973, **9**, (Suppl), 317; *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, **80**, 116302.
- E. MAUPT, W. KOEBERICH, G. ROSAK, J. BEYER and K. SCHOEFFLING, *Arzneim Forsch.*, 1972, **22**, 2198; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, **78**, 106198.
- V. HITZEL, R. WEYER, W. PFATT and K. GEISSEN, *Ger. Offen.*, 2,720,926, Nov 23, 1978; *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **90**, 103843.
- A. P. DELARV, P. J. GABRIEL, Y. PASCAL, *Fr. Demande*, 2, 184, 511, Feb. 1, 1974; *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, **80**, 146020.
- M. K. MADKOUR, M. M. HAMDY, A. M. AWAD and R. M. M. EL-ALLAWY, *J. Drug. Res.*, 1977, **9**, 1; *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, **40**, 406.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd Edn., 1956, p. 853.
- BOLLESTRIN, 1933, **17**, 344, *CL. Soc.*, 2020, 93.
- C. S. WEIL, *Biometrics*, 1952, **8**, 249.